

Appendix

1. Search string customized by database

Database	Keywords set
ACM	("System of Systems" OR "SoS" OR "System-of-Systems") AND ("software architecture" OR "architecture") AND ("analysis" OR "evaluate" OR "test" OR "review" OR "verification" OR "evaluation" OR "assessing" OR "simulating" OR "trade-offs") AND ("quality" OR "non-functional requirement")
IEEE	("System of Systems" OR "SoS" OR "System-of-Systems") AND ("software architecture" OR "architecture" OR "architecting" OR "architectural") AND ("analysis" OR "evaluate" OR "test" OR "review" OR "verification" OR "evaluation" OR "assessing" OR "simulating" OR "trade-offs")
Scopus	(System of System" OR "SoS" OR "System-of-System") AND ("software architecture" OR "architectural" OR "architecting" OR "archite*") AND ("analysis" OR "evaluate" OR "review" OR "verification" OR "evaluation" OR "assessing" OR "simulating" OR "trade-offs")
Web of Science	TS=("System of Systems" OR "SoS" OR "System-of-Systems") AND TS=("software architecture" OR "architecture" OR "architecting" OR "architectural") AND TS=("analysis" OR "evaluate" OR "test" OR "review" OR "verification" OR "evaluation" OR "assessing" OR "simulating" OR "trade-offs")
Science Direct	("System of Systems" OR "SoS" OR "System-of-Systems") AND ("software architecture" OR "architecture" OR "architecting" OR "architectural") AND ("analysis" OR "evaluate" OR "test" OR "review" OR "verification" OR "evaluation" OR "assessing" OR "simulating" OR "trade-offs")

TABLE 1. SEARCH STRING

2. Data extraction form

Data item	Value	RQ
Title	Name of the article	
Authors	Set of Names of the authors	
Year	Year of publication	
Publication type	Name of publication venue	
Type of architecture evaluation	If it was questioning, quantitative or hybrid	RQ1
System properties	Quality attributes that it addresses	RQ2
Attribute number to evaluate	Multi-attribute or just one-attribute	RQ2
References	If it references some property systems, quality models or quality attributes	
Validation type	If it was an Illustration, Case study or Experiment	RQ3

TABLE 2. DATA EXTRACTION FORM